

Measurement of specific leaf area

Latilla L., Brunacci L., Muzzini V.G.

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All opinions expressed in the report reflect only the views of the authors.

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Latilla L.^a, Brunacci L.^a, Muzzini V.G.^a

a – CNR - Research Institute on Terrestrial Ecosystems, SP35d, n. 9, 00010 Montelibretti (RM), Italia

Introduction

Specific leaf area (SLA) is a crucial measurement in plant research¹. It is calculated by dividing the total leaf area of a plant by its dry mass. In simpler terms, it tells us how much leaf surface a plant has for a given amount of biomass².

Plants with higher SLA have more leaf surface area to capture sunlight, which increases their photosynthetic capacity. This means they can produce more food (sugars) through photosynthesis. SLA also influences water loss through evapotranspiration. Plants with high SLA tend to lose more water, which can be a disadvantage in dry environments. Some plants with high SLA may have higher concentrations of defensive compounds, making them less palatable to herbivores. therefore constituting a defense against herbivores.

Plants with high SLA are often referred to as "resource-acquisitive" or "fast-growing" species. They are typically found in environments with abundant resources, such as light and water. These plants tend to grow quickly and have a short lifespan. On the other hand, plants with low SLA are often referred to as "resource-conservative" or "slow-growing" species. They are typically found in environments with limited resources, such as dry or nutrient-poor soils. These plants tend to grow slowly and have a long lifespan.

Climate change is expected to alter the distribution of plant species. As temperatures increase and precipitation patterns change, plants with different SLA strategies may become more or less abundant. Understanding how SLA varies among different plant species and how it responds to environmental changes is important for predicting the impacts of climate change on plant communities.

CNR - Rome 1 Research Area

In line with the Third Mission of universities and research institutes to share scientific knowledge with the public, the CNR Montelibretti Research Area in Rome (42.10576N, 12.63737E) periodically organizes events for secondary school students. This hands-on learning experience will introduce students to the scientific method through the measurement of a specific leaf area. By actively participating in key stages of the scientific process, from leaf sampling to analyzing results, students will gain valuable experience in critical thinking, problem solving, and data interpretation. This activity has the potential to spark students' interest in the fields of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) and inspire them to pursue further scientific exploration.

Measuring SLA involves three steps:

1. **Sampling:** Collect a representative sample of leaves from your plant species. Ensure the leaves are fully expanded and free from damage or disease.
2. **Measuring leaf area:** This can be done using various methods, including leaf area meters, image analysis software, or by tracing leaves onto paper and measuring the area of the tracings.
3. **Measuring dry mass:** The leaves are dried in an oven at a specific temperature (usually around 70°C) until they reach a constant weight. The dry mass is then measured.

1. MEASUREMENT – DATA

The numerical value attributed to a quantity, obtained and expressed as the ratio between the given quantity and another of the same kind taken as a unit (unit of measurement), and determined with appropriate methods or measurement instruments⁴.

The measurement of a physical quantity is an approximation of the true value of the physical quantity.

Accuracy of a measurement

Accuracy means the extent of the difference between the measured value and the true value. The smaller the difference, the greater the accuracy of the measurement.

Precision of a measurement

The precision of a measurement means the extent of the difference between the measurements compared to the average value. The smaller the magnitude of the difference the greater the precision.

2. SAMPLING

Statistical survey strategy which consists in the observation of a part of the units that make up a population in order to obtain valid information for the entire population. The subset of units on which the survey is carried out is called the sample³.

Minimum number of samples to have a standard deviation → 2

$$\text{Deviazione Standard} \rightarrow s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{(n-1)}}$$

Minimum number of safety samples → 3

The sample should be as representative of the population as possible.

3. MEASURING LEAF AREA

To measure the surface of a leaf we can use different methodologies:

A. We can draw the leaf on a sheet of graph paper and count the number of squares enclosed in the drawing (Fig.1).

B. We can draw the leaf on a white sheet of paper and simultaneously draw a geometric figure (for example a square) of known area. Subsequently, the two figures are cut out and weighed (Fig.2). With a simple mathematical ratio it is possible to trace the surface of the "leaf of paper" and therefore of the leaf.

$$A_{leaf} = A_{geometric\ square} * \left(\frac{W_{paper\ leaf}}{W_{paper\ geometric\ square}} \right)$$

A = Surface area; W = Weight

C. We can take a digital image of the leaf and use software to measure its surface.

It is possible to acquire the image in different ways:

1. With a camera → SD → computer
2. With a smartphone → (cloud, mail, etc.) → computer
3. With a webcam → computer
4. With a scanner → computer

It is essential to have a dimensional reference in the photo, an image whose dimensions are known (Fig.3)

Following this last method to "measure" a digital image we can use the open source ImageJ software which can be used on the three most popular operating systems.

- Download from the site <https://imagej.net/ij/>
- Extract the contents of the compressed file and run it
- File → Open Image
- Define the measurement scale
 - Select → Straight Line
 - Draw a line on the reference image (Fig.4)
 - Select → Analyze → Set Scale (Fig.5)
- Set the Color Threshold
 - Select Image → Adjust → Color Threshold (Fig.6)
 - Modify Hue; Saturation; Brightness e deselezionare Dark background
 - Select
- Measure the surface area
 - Select Analyze → Analyze particles (Fig.7)
 - Set Show → Outlines
 - Select → Display results; Clear results; Include holes
 - Select → Ok
- Save table Results

4. MEASURING DRY MASS

Fresh Weight

After sampling the leaves the first step is to determine the fresh weight placing a piece of weighing paper or aluminum foil on the balance and tare it (zero the balance). Place the fresh leaf sample on the paper or foil and record the weight. This is the fresh mass.

Dry Weight

Place the leaf sample(s) on the weighing paper or foil in an oven at 60-70°C until a constant weight is achieved. This may take several days, depending on the thickness and moisture content of the leaves. Remove the dry leaf sample(s) from the oven and allow to cool to room temperature. Weigh the dry leaf sample(s) on the same scale and record the weight. Subtract the weight of the weighing paper or foil from the dry weight to obtain the actual dry mass of the leaf sample.

5. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

If the leaf sample is representative of all the leaves of the plant it is possible to determine the overall leaf surface area of the plant.

$$A_c = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n a_j}{n} \quad A_T = A_c * N_p$$

A_c = Average leaf area of the sample

N_p = Total number of leaves of the plant

A_T = Total Leaf Area

In the same way can determine dry weight total of the plant

$$W_c = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j}{n} \quad W_T = W_c * N_p$$

W_c = Average weight dry of the sample

N_p = Total number of leaves of the plant

W_T = Total Leaf Weight

Finally Specific Leaf Area (SLA) can be determined in two ways:

$$\text{a. } SLA = \frac{A_T}{W_T} \quad \text{b. } SLA = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{a_j}{w_j}\right)}{n}$$

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APPENDIX 1

Fig.1 – Leaf on graph paper

Fig.2 – Paper shapes

Fig.3 – Leaves image

Fig.4 – Reference Line

Fig.5 – Set Scale

Fig.6 – Color Threshold

Fig.7 – Analyze particles